

Individual Educational Trajectory as a Way to Improve the Effectiveness of Learning

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the principles of building an educational trajectory, the phases of its implementation, as well as the individual psychological characteristics of a student that determine an individual educational trajectory. The study showed that the educational process and close contact with the teacher-mentor contributes to the creation of a positive emotional atmosphere, motivating the student to work actively and achieve the set individual educational goals both in the development of professional disciplines and in the study of a foreign language. The results of the study contribute to the expansion of opportunities for organizing the educational process at the university, as well as for the self-management of learning for students together with a mentor.

Keywords: educational trajectory, individual, self-management, individual educational goals, professional disciplines.

Introduction

The modern approach to teaching a foreign language combines traditional teaching methods with the individual work of the teacher with the student, and also involves a large amount of independent work of the student. Individualization of learning occurs through the implementation of individual educational trajectories and routes. However, the implementation of an individually-oriented model of teaching a modern specialist consists in the formation of both professional and communicative competencies, while the development of professional communication skills in a foreign language is considered necessary.

Literature review

Despite the popularity and habitual use of the term "innovation" in the scientific community, with a more detailed reference to it, an understanding of a certain blurring of this concept in the perception of researchers comes. In search of understanding the attitude of modern teachers-researchers in the field of a foreign language to the innovative component of their work, we turned to the publications of domestic authors of recent years [1]. In the works of research teachers devoted to the study of a foreign language, despite the frequent use of terms related to innovation, its broadest interpretation is often given, associated with "transformations in the psychological and pedagogical process" and the introduction of active methods [2], "updating the educational teaching materials" [3], and very rarely the very concept of "innovation" in this area is concretized [4]. Some authors characterize certain parameters of innovative learning, which relate to the quality of relationships and communication, which should be at a high level, understanding the goals of the educational process by students, relying on emotions and feelings of students, flexibility, and feedback [5].

A number of foreign authors come to the conclusion that, in general, the term "innovation" is understood mainly in the economic context, namely as "progress" [4]. And in this context, according to the author, who calls this approach "naive", everything "traditional" from the usual course of lectures to paper versions of a foreign language textbook is subjected to criticism. It is no secret that some "innovations" are commercial in nature and are more related to marketing approaches in the need to implement an educational product. These thoughts are consonant with the ideas of other researchers [2], who believe that the "innovations" of scientists, "university science" basically have economic interests and are associated with the financing of scientific projects.

The second approach in the theoretical understanding of "innovation" in the field of teaching is the approach associated with technological progress. "It is "technologies" that define the features of the modern world: innovations are nothing but their main expression, their language in relation to nature" [2]. In the field of teaching, we are talking in this context about information and communication technologies (ICT).

The third group of researchers believes that innovations in education are associated with social innovations aimed at improving the well-being of individuals or communities [7].

Among the latest innovations, the authors highlight, for example, activity and cognitive approaches in teaching foreign languages, new forms of interaction between a teacher and a student in the educational process, etc.

Based on the above socio-critical approach to innovation in the field of teaching foreign languages, some authors [4] believe that the concept of "innovation in the field of didactics of foreign languages" lies in the plane of technology and economics. And depending on specific interests, the choice may lean in one direction or another.

Discussions

The non-linearity of the educational process in the implementation of an individual educational route provides great opportunities for independent work of a student, which contributes to the effective formation of professionally significant skills of a future specialist, one of which is professional communication, while in the context of globalization and international integration, professional communication of a specialist in a foreign language comes to the fore. language.

The implementation of professional communication in a foreign language is a competitive advantage for a specialist in the labor market [8]. Teaching a foreign language to adults (students) is characterized by high motivation for learning and communication, attention to professional semantic load, and a certain degree of self-control [2]. The process of teaching a foreign language to adults has a number of positive features compared to working with students, for example: the ability to abstract and use life and professional experience, the ability to set and achieve goals, the ability to communicate with a teacher and other students; the ability to develop your own learning strategies, the ability to plan your time.

Teaching a foreign language to specialists in non-linguistic specialties is aimed at developing students' communicative, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies. This approach is based on the state educational standard, which involves the formation of a specialist at least a basic level of foreign language proficiency, namely the formation of communication skills in the social, public and professional spheres.

In addition to individual value orientations, a student-centered approach relies on the individual psychological characteristics of the student, which largely determine his individual educational trajectory [5]. These features are: the level of intelligence (the ability to acquire

knowledge, acquire skills and be able to apply them to solve professional problems); creativity (analytical abilities to generate new knowledge); learning motivation (feelings about (not) achieving learning goals); self-esteem. In addition to the "traditional" psychological characteristics of the individual, they distinguish social intelligence (communicative competence aimed at establishing contact and maintaining it to solve the task), which is necessary in modern conditions both in the implementation of an individual training program and in professional life.

Self-managed education of an adult (student) is closely related to individual cognitive characteristics. The perception of information and the formation of knowledge consist of three stages: sensory (the significance of information is determined); information synthesis; selection and concentration of information in the short-term memory of the student, and then in his long-term memory. Processing and storage of information in short-term memory and retrieval from long-term memory in the learning process depends on the characteristics of the emotional-motivational system of the individual. Therefore, the organization of the learning process in the form of a multi-level system of current knowledge control with the active participation of the student is an effective tool for active learning, i.e. implementation of an individual educational trajectory. Individualization of the approach occurs in the formation of the content of control and measuring materials, determining the volume of the training course, forms and frequency of control of assimilation of the material [2].

The individualization of the curriculum requires a revision of the knowledge assessment system. To this end, it is advisable to introduce a rating system for assessing knowledge. Such a system gives an additional incentive to the student, since it does not suppress the student if he shows a low result, and motivates him to further creative work and active educational activity with high rating scores.

Today, the point-rating system is introduced not only when students master general educational and professionally oriented disciplines, but also when learning a foreign language. The work of students is evaluated on a 100-point scale. Points are distributed for all types in practical classes during the training weeks. The student's activity is assessed as follows: work in the classroom, homework, test results, independent work (preparation of conversational topics), presentation at student conferences (reward points). By the time of the midterm control, the

scores are summed up, which makes it possible to quantify the work of the student and identify the dynamics of individual development.

The introduction of a point-rating system of assessment has a stimulating effect on the student and leads to an increase in the quality of the student's independent preparation and his work in the classroom. In addition, this approach is a more objective and visual assessment system, as it allows the student to track and create their own rating. At the beginning of the semester, students are provided with individual tasks, clear criteria for evaluating each type of work are explained to them, the contribution of each type of activity to the final grade is determined, the maximum and minimum points are set, as well as bonus points.

The opportunity to participate, track and correct their progress in learning a foreign language, together with the development of an individual educational trajectory, has a positive impact on the student, being an emotional and motivating tool for acquiring professional knowledge and forming linguistic and communicative competencies.

When implementing an individual trajectory, independent intellectual activity is the basis of the educational process against the background of the traditional approach. Individualization of the program and personal work with the student contributes to the activation of all mechanisms of perception and processing of information (memory, attention, thinking, emotions). The individual pace and volume of educational work activate cognitive activity, improve the abstract and analytical activity of the student, motivate active creative work, which contributes not only to the implementation of an individual educational trajectory, but also to the formation of the professional personality of the future graduate.

The mentioned cognitive, motivational and emotional aspects have a great influence on the formation of the professional personality of a modern specialist, which is impossible without creating a stable motivation for learning foreign languages. Linguistic competencies are developed on the basis of three main principles: communicative, cognitive and personal. Achieving success in the implementation of a foreign language learning strategy within the framework of an individual educational trajectory is determined by the communicative needs of a specialist, his cognitive tasks and personal expectations.

The professionalism of a modern specialist is determined by his professional achievements, psychological characteristics, as well as the value orientations that guided him in obtaining a

specialized education, his internal resources and motivation. At the same time, such qualities as awareness of the need and the ability to bring the level of one's professional training in line with professional requirements, the ability to self-develop and compensate for missing professional qualities, the ability to perform professional duties with high quality, high labor productivity, and the sustainability of high results can and should be instilled in the period of formation specialist, i.e. while studying at a university in the course of implementing an individual educational trajectory. In addition to the above competencies, a modern specialist needs to form communicative competencies in their native and foreign languages. The development of linguistic and communicative competencies is closely related to one of the strategies for implementing an individual educational route, taking into account the individual psychological and cognitive characteristics of the student.

Conclusion

The set goals are achieved with the active cooperation of the teacher and the student. At the same time, from a methodological point of view, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following activities: the creation of training programs taking into account the specifics of the profession; the selection of language material, as well as the development of communicative creative tasks and speech situations of a professional orientation; organization and ensuring the interaction of students in solving problematic problems of a professional orientation. Such an approach will allow forming a basic professional background of knowledge in a foreign language, while training and implementing professional communication skills will create the necessary motivational and emotional environment.

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